

FUNCTIONS OF THE PRINCIPLE OF LEGAL CERTAINTY

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Annotasia:

In works on the principles of law, their functions are not fully distinguished or can be listed without disclosing the content, and only in individual scientific research this issue is considered in sufficient detail. At the same time, consideration of the principles of law reflecting the essence of law and the content of its leading ideas and principles that form the basis of legal regulation will not be complete without considering the functions of the principle of legal certainty in this paragraph.

From the point of view of the functions of the principle of legal certainty as a specific principle of law, we must pay attention to such issues as its impact on legal regulation, its place and importance in the legal system.

The principles of law determine the behavior of participants in legal relations and are part of the regulatory mechanism.

Keywords: function, legal accuracy, regulator, stability, gap filling, regulatory control, legal practice, uncertainty

Introduction

As you know, the concept of "function" has different meanings. In philosophy, the concept of function refers to the elements that affect it, depending on another phenomenon. A function also refers to a job, a role, the meaning of something, a duty, and a field of activity performed by a mathematical law, object, or system¹. Also, the function is understood as the directional, selective influence of the system on certain aspects of the external environment². In this dissertation, the function is studied in the sense of the direction of impact, function. It should be noted that, despite the fact that the question of the independent and direct influence of legal principles on subjects of law and their actions is controversial in national scientific research, depending on the type of legal principles, scientists distinguish their various functions. The rule of law, as a general and universal function inherent in all principles, can take as an initial approach a regulatory (regulatory) function that has a very large content. Summarizing the scientific views on this issue, three

¹ Толковый словарь русского языка: 80 000 слов и фразеологических выражений / под ред. – С. И. Ожегова, Н. Ю. Шведовой. М.:Атберг 98, 2010. – С. 847.

² Свидерский В.И., Зобов Р. А. Новые философские аспекты элементарно-структурных отношений. Л., 1970. – С. 42.

main points can be identified in the content of the regulatory function of the principles of law. V.V.Oxamitny agrees with the opinion on the normative significance of the principles of law, believing that it is impossible to absolutize the possibilities of their direct impact on the individual³.

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R.K.Rusinov also argues that the population cannot know thousands of legal norms in detail, nevertheless, the main task of state bodies is to act lawfully, based on legal principles⁴. V.V. According to Oxamitny, the role and importance of the norms of law should not be underestimated, even if such conclusions are made without taking into account the fact that the principles of law are implemented directly and through an integral system of norms of law. Moreover, one of the directions of the regulatory impact of the principles of law for the legislator is their fundamental role in the creation of legal norms, one should agree with this opinion⁵.

This is due to the fact that, according to some scientists, their regulatory role is manifested only when there are gaps in legislation, and this situation does not always repeat itself. For this reason, N.A.Arapov evaluates the regulatory function of the principles of law as optional⁶.

In our opinion, firstly, the regulatory function of the principle of legal certainty is highly optional in the civil law family, whereas in law enforcement the function of "filling gaps" is primary. Secondly, the principles of law determine the main content of the norms of a system, branch or institution of law⁷, It serves as a starting point for further improvement of legislation and law enforcement practice⁸. That is, the regulatory function of the principles of law at the stage of lawmaking is that they set a certain direction for the further development of the legal system and should be taken into account by the

³ Оксамытный В.В. Правомерное поведение личности. Киев, 1990– С. 51.

⁴ Русинов Р. К. Сознание и правомерное поведение личности // Советское государство и право, 1983. № 5. – С. 8 ; Радько Т. Н. Социалистическое правосознание и воспитательные функции права // Труды Высшей следственной школы МВД СССР. Волгоград, 1973. Вып. 8. – С. 56.

⁵ Оксамытный В. В. Правомерное поведение личности. – С. 51.

⁶ Арапов Н. А. Фидуциарное государство и правомерные ожидания (на основе принципа поддержания доверия). — Санкт-Петербург : Изд-во С.-Петерб. ун-та, 2020. – С. 21.

⁷ Принципы российского права: общетеоретический и отраслевой аспекты. – С. 91 ; Волосатова Л. В. Принцип разумности в реализации субъективных гражданских прав : дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. – М., 2005. – С. 35.

⁸ Иванов А. А. Принцип законности юридической ответственности : дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. Тольятти, 2010. – С.

legislator. Such an influence of the principles of law in the scientific literature is called differently. N.A. Considering the functions of the principles of constitutional law, Arapov considers constructivism, which consists in forcing the legislator to adopt laws and develop their ideas in accordance with the principles of constitutional law, one of the main⁹.

The stabilizing function of the principle of legal certainty is common to the stages of individualization and concretization of rights and obligations, as well as law enforcement and implementation. At the stage of individualization and concretization of rights and obligations, the participants in the relevant legal relations are interested in the appearance of a specific result inherent in the normative model, and it is very important for them that an arbitrary change in their status is not allowed.

Conclusion

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the principle of legal certainty is characterized by the fact that it has functions that affect legal relations and combines such optional functions as regulatory (regulating), stabilizing, filling in gaps, regulatory Control, ensuring legal security. Its functions can be summarized briefly below: Firstly, compliance with the principle of legal certainty is a natural and objective requirement in legal practice, especially in the process of rulemaking. This legal regulatory function enters the arena, influencing the reduction of the abstraction of norms of this type by bringing norms into the form necessary for their direct application and implementation. Secondly, the function of the principle of legal certainty to eliminate contradictions in the norms of law in legal practice, to prevent inaccuracies, is a logical solution to the problem of legal uncertainty. Thirdly, legal certainty has a fundamental function that ensures legal regulation and legal security, and concretization is carried out depending on the availability of grounds and within the appropriate boundaries. Fourth, the role of legal accuracy in the interpretation of normative legal acts contained in the current forms of national legislation and in ensuring legal security is high, which requires the coverage of powerful thought processes.

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⁹ Арапов Н. А. Фидуциарное государство и правомерные ожидания (на основе принципа поддержания доверия). — Санкт-Петербург : Изд-во С.-Петерб. ун-та, 2020. – С. 24.

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